

Supporting Information

Intraparticle heterogeneity limits capacity in lithium-sulfur batteries with carbonate electrolyte

Ayca Senol Gungor¹, Jean-Marc von Mentlen¹, Francisco Javier García-Soriano², Christian Zaubitzer³, Milivoj Plodinec³, Jean G. A. Ruthes⁴, Sven Dunkel⁵, Volker Presser^{4,6,7}, Alen Vizintin², Vanessa Wood^{1,*}, Christian Prehal^{5,*}

1 Department of Information Technology and Electrical Engineering, ETH Zürich, Gloriastrasse 35, 8092 Zürich, Switzerland

2 Department of Materials Chemistry, National Institute of Chemistry, Hajdrihova ulica 19, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

3 Scientific Center for Optical and Electron Microscopy, ScopeM, ETH Zürich, Otto-Stern-Weg 3, 8093 Zürich, Switzerland

4 INM - Leibniz Institute for New Materials, Campus D2 2, 66123 Saarbrücken, Germany

5 Department of Chemistry and Physics of Materials, University of Salzburg, Jakob-Haringer-Straße 2a, 5020 Salzburg, Austria

6 Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Saarland University, Campus D2 2, 66123 Saarbrücken, Germany

7 saarene – Saarland Center for Energy Materials and Sustainability, Campus C4 2, 66123 Saarbrücken, Germany

Figure S1: Raman spectra of AC08 powders prepared with different ball milling speeds. Ball milling does not cause significant structural changes in the carbon structure.

Figure S2: TGA results of AC08 powders with prepared with different ball milling speeds. All measurements confirm successful melt infiltration into the pores at a C-S ratio of 1:1 and the absence of surface sulfur. The sulfur and non-ball-milled C-S powder data (single reference curve) were previously published in Ref. 1 and are included here for comparison. All other data shown are newly acquired.

Figure S3: Long term cycling performance of electrodes prepared at different ball milling speeds with a mass ratio of 1:1. (a) Galvanostatic gravimetric discharge capacities and (b) total discharge capacities (at the rate of C/10) with different carbon indicated by color tones and shapes. Coulombic efficiencies are represented on the right axis.

Figure S4: Normalized relaxation curves of electrodes prepared at different ball milling speeds (mass ratio 1:1), recorded at OCV during GITT. Curves correspond to (a-c) non-ball milled (d-f) 500-rpm ball milled and (g-i) 800-rpm ball milled electrodes during first delithiation, first delithiation and second lithiation, respectively. Color tones represent different discharge capacities. Relaxation time constants were approximated by identifying the time at which the normalized relaxation voltage decayed to $1/e$. An explicit exponential fitting was deliberately avoided, as the true relaxation behavior is governed by a superposition of multiple exponential processes with a complex distribution of time constants.

Figure S5: Reference EELS spectra based on Gatan EELS Atlas. (a) The reference spectrum for LiF deposit on C film, a comparable EELS spectrum. The peak around 62 eV and the shoulder around 70 eV represent the characteristic features of LiF. (b) As a comparable reference EELS spectrum of S deposited on a C film, showing the major edge of $L_{2,3}$ at 165 eV.

Figure S6: Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) measurements for 800 rpm ball milled particles after the first discharge. (a) Representative transmission electron micrographs of the CEI, which appears as a heterogeneous layer composed of crystalline phases, solid clusters, and organic phases (blob-like structures). (b) Crystalline Li_2S (111) and LiF (111) phases marked on a discharged particle. As particles were scratched off from the electrodes, binder residues are also present.

Figure S7: Scanning electron micrographs of electrodes after the first discharge: (a) non-ball milled (b) 500-rpm ball milled and (c) 800-rpm ball milled. (a) The non-ball milled electrode with an approximate size of 10-12 μm and the zoomed in micrographs. As seen in micrograph (3) the particle surface is smooth, and the particle is intact. (b) Activated carbon particles after the first discharge. The particles exhibit cracks because of the volume expansion during CEI and Li_2S formation and the stress on the carbon backbone. Surface deposits may correspond to CEI components. (c) 800-rpm ball milled electrodes after the first discharge. There are fewer cracks compared to large particles, but surface deposits are still visible after lithiation and CEI formation.

Figure S8: Representative spherical masks used for particle size distribution analysis. The detailed explanation is given in the Methods section. At least 300 random particles were masked as spheres for each ball-milling speed. Particle diameters were determined by color-thresholding of sphere areas and plotted as Gaussian size distribution curves.

Supporting Tables

Table S1: Detailed XPS data representing elemental content in atomic percent.

Element	Content (at%)	
	Not BM	800-BM
Li	25	31
C	33	27.5
O	24	18
F	16	21
P	1	1
S	1	1.5

Table S2. Type of function, binding energies (BE), full width half maxima (FWHM), and source of the C 1s deconvoluted spectra in Figure 4.

Species	Peak Type	BE (eV)	FWHM (eV)	Source
Si-CH ₃	Voigt	284.4 ± 0.1	1.3 ± 0.1	tape
C-C/C=C	Voigt	285.2 ± 0.1	1.3 ± 0.1	CEI / Cathode
C-O-C	Voigt	286.2 ± 0.1	1.3 ± 0.1	Electrolyte
C-F	Voigt	287.2 ± 0.1	1.3 ± 0.1	FEC decomposition electrolyte decomposition
O-C=O	Voigt	289.0 ± 0.1	1.3 ± 0.1	Electrolyte decomposition
CO ₃ ²⁻	Voigt	289.9 ± 0.1	1.3 ± 0.1	DMC decomposition/ residual electrolyte

Table S3. Type of function, binding energies (BE), full width half maxima (FWHM) and source of the F 1s deconvoluted spectra in Figure 4.

Species	Peak Type	BE (eV)	FWHM (eV)	Source
Li-F	Voigt	685.5 ± 0.1	1.5 ± 0.1	FEC LiPF ₆ decomposition
C-F (from FEC)	Voigt	686.3 ± 0.1	1.5 ± 0.1	FEC
C-F	Voigt	687.8 ± 0.1	1.5 ± 0.1	FEC decomposition
PF ₆ / POF ₃	Voigt	688.9 ± 0.1	1.5 ± 0.1	LiPF ₆

Table S4. Type of function, binding energies (BE), full width half maxima (FWHM) and source of the P 1p deconvoluted spectra in Figure 4.

Species	Peak Type	BE (eV)	FWHM (eV)	Source
POF ₃ / LiPOx	Voigt	134.2 ± 0.1	2.6 ± 0.1	LiPF ₆ decomposition
PF ₆	Voigt	136.0 ± 0.1	2.6 ± 0.1	LiPF ₆

Table S5. Type of function, binding energies (BE), full width half maxima (FWHM) and source of the S 2p deconvoluted spectra in Figure 4.

Species	Peak Type	BE (eV)	FWHM (eV)	Source
S-Li	Voigt ($2p_{3/2}$)	160.7 ± 0.1	1.3 ± 0.1	Li ₂ S
S-S-Li	Voigt ($2p_{3/2}$)	162.0 ± 0.1	1.3 ± 0.1	Li ₂ S _x
S-S	Voigt ($2p_{3/2}$)	163.7 ± 0.2	1.3 ± 0.1	S ₈ and Li ₂ S _x
S-C	Voigt ($2p_{3/2}$)	164.6 ± 0.2	1.3 ± 0.1	
S-O	Voigt ($2p_{3/2}$)	169.7 ± 0.1	1.4 ± 0.2	Oxidize sulfur (decomposition) Li ₂ SO ₄

Table S6. Type of function, binding energies (BE), full width half maxima (FWHM) and source of the Li 1s deconvoluted spectra in Figure 4.

Species	Peak Type	BE (eV)	FWHM (eV)	Source
LiF	Voigt	53.4 ± 0.4	1.4 ± 0.1	F 2s loss peak overlap
Li _x S _y	Voigt	54.7 ± 0.2	1.4 ± 0.1	Li ₂ S _x
LiF	Voigt	55.7 ± 0.1	1.4 ± 0.1	CEI formation, decomposition
LiOR	Voigt	56.3 ± 0.1	1.4 ± 0.1	Electrolyte decomposition

References

(1) Senol Gungor, A.; von Mentlen, J. M.; Ruthes, J. G. A.; Garcia-Soriano, F. J.; Drvaric Talian, S.; Presser, V.; Porcar, L.; Vizintin, A.; Wood, V.; Prehal, C. Understanding Rate and Capacity Limitations in Li-S Batteries Based on Solid-State Sulfur Conversion in Confinement. *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces* **2024**, *16* (49), 67651-67661. DOI: 10.1021/acsami.4c13183.